

INNOVATIVE GEOREFERENCED METAGENOMICS: A NEW FRONTIER IN PREVENTING TROJAN HORSES IN GLOBAL AGRICULTURE

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Annotation. *Georeferenced metagenomics is a revolutionary way to prevent the spread of “Trojan horses” in global agriculture, including invasive species, pathogens, and genetically modified organisms (GMOs) with unintended ecological effects. By combining advanced metagenomic sequencing with geospatial analysis, this method enables the precise identification and mapping of harmful microorganisms and invasive species in agricultural landscapes. By using this technology, threats can be detected early, spreads can be accurately tracked, and targeted interventions can be developed to protect crops and ecosystems. The integration of georeferenced metagenomics into agricultural practices can significantly enhance biosecurity measures, improve pest and disease management, and mitigate the risks associated with global trade and climate change. This approach, which is a new frontier in agricultural science, provides a vital tool for safeguarding global food security and biodiversity by proactively addressing potential threats before they become widespread.*

Keywords: *georeferenced metagenomics, pathogen detection, bioinformatics, agricultural biosecurity, disease management.*

The concept of a "Trojan horse" in plants refers to the introduction of GMOs or invasive species into ecosystems, which often have the potential to cause significant harm or disruption. The term "Trojan horse" originates from the ancient Greek myth, wherein a deceptive strategy was employed to infiltrate and ultimately conquer a fortified city. In plant biology, it encompasses various scenarios, including the spread of pathogens, pests, or unintended consequences of biotechnology. One of the primary global threats associated with Trojan horses in plants is the introduction of invasive species. Certain plants, whether introduced intentionally or accidentally, can become invasive, outcompeting native species and disrupting local ecosystems [1]. For instance, kudzu in the United States and water hyacinth in Africa have both become highly invasive, obstructing waterways and displacing native flora. Another significant threat is genetic pollution, where the introduction of genetically modified plants leads to the unintentional transfer of modified genes to wild relatives through cross-pollination. This genetic contamination can result in a loss of biodiversity, the emergence of herbicide-resistant superweeds, and broader ecological imbalances. Furthermore, biological control efforts can sometimes have unintended consequences. In some instances, biological control agents, such as insects or microorganisms introduced to manage pests, may attack non-target species, causing ecological damage [2]. A well-known example is the cane toad in Australia, which was initially introduced to control pests in sugarcane fields but has since become a threat to native wildlife. The deployment of GMOs in agriculture has raised concerns about unintended consequences, such as the development of resistance in pests and adverse effects on non-target organisms, including beneficial insects and

soil microorganisms. These outcomes can introduce new challenges in managing pests and diseases. Additionally, the movement of plants across borders can facilitate the spread of plant pathogens, which can act as Trojan horses, further complicating efforts to maintain ecological balance and agricultural productivity [3]. The aim of this study is to focus on exploring the potential help with geo-referenced metagenomics as a cutting-edge tool to detect, understand, and prevent these biological threats.

The first step in georeferenced metagenomics involves collecting environmental samples, such as soil, water, or plant surfaces, from specific locations. Each sample is precisely tagged with geographical coordinates using GPS technology. This georeferencing process is crucial as it links microbial data to the exact location of the sample, enabling spatial analysis and correlation with environmental factors. Once the samples are collected, they undergo metagenomic sequencing, which involves extracting and sequencing the total DNA present in the sample [4]. Unlike traditional approaches that target specific organisms, metagenomic sequencing captures all genetic material, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the microbial community, including bacteria, fungi, viruses, and other microorganisms. This figure illustrates the mechanisms of georeferenced metagenomics, a novel approach integrating metagenomic sequencing with geospatial data to analyze microbial communities in specific environmental contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mechanisms of georeferenced metagenomics.

The sequencing data are processed using advanced bioinformatics tools to assemble and annotate the genetic information. This analysis includes identifying taxonomic groups, functional genes, and potential pathogenic traits [4]. The resulting data provide insights into the diversity, abundance, and functional potential of the microbial communities in each georeferenced location. The metagenomic data are then integrated with geospatial information, such as soil type, climate, land use, and topography, using Geographic Information Systems (GIS). This integration allows researchers to explore spatial patterns, identify hotspots of microbial activity, and assess environmental factors influencing microbial distributions. By examining these correlations, it becomes possible to predict areas at risk for the spread of invasive species or pathogens. Advanced mapping and visualization techniques are employed to represent the spatial distribution of microbial communities across landscapes. These visualizations help researchers and decision-makers understand the complex interactions between microbial populations and their environments, enabling the identification of key areas for intervention. The integrated data are used to develop predictive models that forecast the spread of pathogens or invasive species based on current and historical trends. These models serve as decision-support tools, guiding strategies

for managing agricultural biosecurity, optimizing pest and disease control measures, and informing policy decisions. Thus, georeferenced metagenomics offers a comprehensive view of microbial diversity and functionality within a specific location by analyzing the entire genetic content of a sample. This holistic approach ensures the detection and analysis of all relevant microorganisms, including potential threats. By integrating microbial data with precise geographic locations, georeferenced metagenomics allows for the examination of spatial patterns and relationships, thereby enhancing our understanding of how environmental factors influence microbial communities [5]. This spatial context is crucial for identifying regions at risk of pathogen spread or ecological disruption. Additionally, georeferenced metagenomics is versatile across various scales, from small plots to large landscapes, making it applicable to a broad spectrum of research needs and applications. This scalability facilitates targeted interventions at multiple levels, ranging from local farms to national agricultural policies. One of the most valuable applications of georeferenced metagenomics is its capacity for early detection of invasive species, pathogens, or environmental changes, which is essential for implementing timely and effective measures to prevent the establishment and spread of harmful organisms. Ultimately, the insights gained from georeferenced metagenomics provide a robust scientific foundation for decision-making in agriculture, conservation, and environmental management, enabling stakeholders to make informed choices that enhance biosecurity and promote sustainable agricultural practices. This work was supported by the Azerbaijan Science Foundation-Grant AEF-MCG-2022-1(42)-12/07/3-M-07.

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